

Impact of Income Structure to Profitability: Empirical Evidence from Life Insurance Industry in Nepal

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Abstract

This paper has two objectives: first it explores the income structure and their trend. Second, it aims to confirm whether the income structure and financial performance have any significant difference on younger and older firms. This paper obtained data from the financial statements of eight life insurance companies for five years period (2007/08 to 2011/12). Seven parameters of sources of income and four parameters of profitability and earnings analyses and arrives into conclusion using descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation and t test along with descriptive statistics. This study concludes that age of firm influence the income structure but it is indifferent in profitability and earnings. Similarly types of income sources and Net Profit Margin and Return on Asset have negative but Return on Equity have positive correlation. The main implication of this study is that it contributes additionally to understand the income structure of the life insurance companies and their relationship with profitability in general and to explore differences on financial performances between younger and older firms in particular.

INTRODUCTION

Life insurance provides unique services to individual, private sector and government. It collects resources and mobilizes through different channels in one hand and it shares the risk and provides financial compensation in case of any unexpected events occurs. The risk absorption role of insurers promotes financial stability in the financial markets and provides a "sense of peace" to economic entities. The way of risk sharing, risk pooling and compensating the risk is different between life and non life insurers but the common objective of both sectors is earning profit. Income is basic requirement of any business organization to earn profit. Life insurance companies have several sources of income. present their income statements as per the prevailing accounting standards of particular economy, laws of land and as per the instruction of insurance regulator. Life insurers collect large amount of funds as premium which is long term liability of policyholders. Life premium amount is sum of saving component, which to be returned back to the policyholders or beneficiaries and risk component (Agrawal, 2010). Short term plan (term) insurance premium can be recognized as income end of the same year but long term plan insurance premium such as whole-life contracts (including limited-payment and single-premium life contracts), guaranteed renewable term life contracts, endowment contracts, annuity contracts, and title insurance contracts, shall be recognized as revenue when due from policyholders.

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Nepalese life insurance industry has undergone with significant change over the last few years. Insurance Board has instructed to all life insurers to increase the minimum paid up capital of life insurance company from Rs. 250 million to Rs. 500 million, it has already introduced the Corporate Good Governance Directives, Solvency Margin Directives, Directives of Preparation of Financial Statements, Investment Directives, Insurer's Earmarked Related Directives, 2009, Insurer Merger and Acquisition Directives, 2013 and Nepalese Mortality Table, 2009 (www.bsib.org.np). These provisions have been affecting the insurance industries multifaceted. Some provisions reduce expenditure and another one increase and reverse effect we can see in profitability side. These directives effect on cost of business, cost of equity, return and risk of the investment assets in one hand and in another hand these provisions also encourage to reduce the unnecessary management expenditure.

Among 9 life insurers, 8 are doing only life business and one is doing both life and non life business. In this study only life insurers are included. In aggregate, life insurance industries (excluding state owned insurer) hold Rs. 5058, million equity capital, Rs. 51830 million total assets Rs. 46,772 million life fund end of FY 2012/13.

Nepalese Life insurance companies are required to follow the "Directives of Preparation of Financial Statements of Life Insurers, 2009" and Long Form Audit Report to prepare the financial statements. These directive and report are issued by Insurance Board of Nepal. Besides directives, number of other circulars and direction also require to follow to prepare the financial statements. Both cash and accrual policies are applied while recognize the income. First, Revenue Account is prepared, after that Profit and Loss Account is prepared and on the basis of these accounts, Balance Sheet is prepared. There are 31 schedules to be disclosed while preparing the Financial Statements. The revenue is required to disclose by schedule 1, 2 and 3. Basis of income recognition on each type of income is mentioned in brief in table 2.

Accounting Headings of revenue of life insurers are divided into 7 different sub headings which is depicted in table 2 in brief.

Table 2: Revenue Headings and Description

Headings of Revenue (Income)	Descriptions	Basis of Accountings	Directives reference ¹
1. Net Premium	<p>Net premium = Gross premium – Ceded commission on Reinsurance</p> <p>Direct Premium = First premium + Renewal premium and one time premium</p> <p>Gross premium = Net Premium + Reinsurance ceded fee</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cash basis for regular premium • Recognized as deposit if premium receipt in advance 	Annex 1
2. Reinsurance Commission Income	Amount paid to Reinsurance company as a insurance premium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accrual basis • Profit commission in cash basis 	Annex 1

¹ Directives for Preparation of Financial Statements for Life Insurers, Prepared by Insurance Board Nepal, 2009

3. Investment, Loan and Others income	Interest income from fixed deposits and investment on debenture, return on government securities, dividend income from share, capital gain,	• Accrual basis	Annex 2
4. Loan against Policy income	Interest earnings from loan given to policyholders	• Accrual basis	Annex 3
5. Other Direct Income	Penalty, late fee and charges, stamp income, photocopy charge etc.	• Accrual basis and Cash basis	Revenue Account
6. Provision for Outstanding Claim beginning of the year	Provision excess over actual claim	Amount of Actuarial valuation or 50 percent of net premium whichever is higher	Revenue Account
7. Provision for unexpired risk at the beginning of the year	provisioned amount excess over actual risk amount	on proportionate basis	Revenue Account

Source: Directives of Preparation of Financial Statements of Life Insurance, 2009, Insurance Board

The remaining part of the paper is organized in four sections: the second section accounts the past researches on the same area, third section discusses about methodology, fourth section is related to data analysis, and discussion and the result and last section conclude the study on the basis of entire discussion.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Less attention has been given to the revenue structure of the life insurance companies and its impacts on profitability of firm in Nepalese insurance industry. Plentiful studies are carried out in abroad. The revenue structure plays vital role on profitability of company.

Profitability is gradually being popular area of interest of to managers, academicians and tax authorities. Although profitability has been widely investigated in manufacturing industries, far less attention has been paid to it in the financial sector. Profitability related studies have been carried out in the sector of insurance during last decades. A study in insurance sector of Bosnia and Herzegovina was conducted by Pervan, Curak and Marijanovic in 2012 during the period from 2005 to 2010 using first-differenced GMM estimator. The results of the empirical analysis revealed negative and significant influence of claims ratio on profitability and significant positive influence of age, market share and past performance on current profitability.

Chen and Wong (2004) and Mike Adams (1996) find that size, investment and liquidity are major determinants for profitability, Molyneux and Thornton (1992) identified a strong positive association between efficiency and profitability, Malik (2011) suggest that size and capital have strong positive association with insurers' profitability, loss ratio and leverage have strong inverse relationship with profitability and Miller and Noulas (1997) identify an inverse connection between credit risk and profitability.

Charumathi, B. (2012) finds on Indian life insurance context that profitability of life insurers is positively and significantly influenced by the size (as explained by logarithm of net premium) and liquidity. The leverage, premium growth and logarithm of equity capital negatively and significantly influence the profitability of Indian life insurers. This study does not find any evidence for the relationship between underwriting risk and profitability.

There is separate standard to present the financial statements of firm Financial Reporting Standards and other prevailing rules of regulating authorities Income of life insurance firms presented in revenue account

separating in different headings according. There are somehow similarities on practice of presenting the income in different countries. The income heads of 6 Life insurance companies from India, Pakistan, U.K, Japan and Trinidad is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Income Heads of by different Insurance Companies

<p>Bajaj Allianz Life Insurance Co. Ltd, India</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Premium 2. Reinsurance ceded 3. Reinsurance accepted 4. Interest, Dividend & Rent - Gross 5. Profit on sale / redemption of investments 6. Transfer / Gain on revaluation / change in fair value 7. Other investment income 	<p>State Life Insurance Corporation of Pakistan</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Premium less reinsurances 2. Rental income from investment properties 3. Net investment income 4. Regular premium individual policies 5. First year 6. Second year renewals 7. Subsequent year renewals
<p>Nippon Life Insurance Company, Japan</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Revenues from insurance and reinsurance 2. Investment income 3. Interest, dividends, and other income 4. Gain from assets held in trust, 5. Net Gain on sales of securities 6. Gain on redemptions of securities 7. Gain on derivative financial instruments, net 8. Reversal of allowance for doubtful accounts 9. Other investment income 10. Gain from separate accounts, net 	<p>The Guyana and Trinidad Mutual Life Insurance Company Limited, Trinidad</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Insurance premiums 2. Reinsurance premiums 3. Income from investments 4. Other Income 5. Currency Translation Adjustments 6. Adjustment to fair value of investments 7. Net increase in group pension contribution and interest on deposit administration fund 8. Increase in revaluation reserve
<p>Fubon Life Insurance Co. Ltd., UK</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Direct written premiums 2. Reinsurance premiums 3. Net changes in unearned premium reserves 4. Retained earned premium 5. Reinsurance commission income 6. Handling fee incomes 7. Net gain or loss on investment 	<p>Irish Life Assurance Plc., UK</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Premium on insurance contracts 2. Reinsurer's share of premiums on insurance 3. Investment return 4. Fees from investment contract 5. Fees, commission and other income

Source: Compilation from Annual Reports 1

METHODOLOGY

The objective of this paper is to confirm whether the pattern and structure of different source of income of life insurance companies is influenced by age of company. In this study, firms are categorized in two groups: firm having the age 5 years and below are categorized under new firms and above are categorized under old firms (see table 1). The paper has examined the differences of pattern and structure of income and profitability on the basis of age. Net income and Return on equity, return on assets, return on investment and net profit margin are considered as profitability related variables and seven different income sources (see table 2) are considered as income related variables.

Data Source

The study is based on secondary data. Data has been obtained from the annual reports and Annual Financial Statements for 5 fiscal years (2007/08 to 2011/2012) and Quarterly reports. Publication of Insurance Board of Nepal also reviewed. Data are taken from Number of research journals, newspapers and prevailing Acts, Rules, Directives has been consulted and reviewed.

Out of Nine life insurers, eight companies has taken for study. Rastriya Beema Sansthan, has excluded due to the lack of data under study period. for all 8 companies (National Life, Nepal Life, MetAlico and Life Insurance Corporation, Asian life, Surya Life, Gurans life and Prime life). The reliability of data and the calculation is entirely based on annual reports and in the lack of primary data, further verification is not possible. The study is entirely based on secondary data so that might be suffered by the inherent quality of secondary data.

The Hypothesis

Following two hypotheses has been formulated and tested.

H_0 : Income structure of old and new firms have no significant difference.

H_0 : Return on equity, Return on Assets, Net Profit Margin and Return on Investment of old and new firms have no significant difference.

Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics has been used to analyze the data and arrived into conclusion. Hypotheses have been tested using independent t test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Explanation of Variables

Abbreviation, full form and its description of major sources of income, profitability related variables are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Abbreviation and Description of Income and profitability related Variables

Abbreviation	Variable	Description	Measurement Unit
i. NPREM	Net Premium	Net premium shown in Revenue account (serial no. 1)	Rs. in million
ii. RECOMI	Reinsurance Commission Income	Reinsurance Commission Income shown in Revenue account (serial no. 2)	Rs. in million
iii. ILOI	Investment, Loan and Others income	Investment, Loan and Others income shown in Revenue account (serial no. 3)	Rs. in million
iv. LPI	Loan against Policy income	Loan against Policy income shown in Revenue account (serial no. 4)	Rs. in million
v. ODI	Other Direct Income	Other Direct Income shown in Revenue account (serial no. 5)	Rs. in million
vi. POCBY	Provision for Outstanding Claim beginning of the year	Provision for Outstanding Claim beginning of the year shown in Revenue account (serial no. 6)	Rs. in million

		Provision for unexpired risk at the Beginning of the year	Provision for unexpired risk at the Beginning of the year shown in Revenue account (serial no. 7)	Rs. in million
vii. PURBY				
viii. NP	Net Profit		Total income minus total expenses (from Profit and Loss Account)	Rs. in million
ix. NPM	Net Profit Margin		Net Profit/Total Income	percentage
x. ROA	Return on Assets		Net profit After Tax / Total Assets	percentage
xi. ROE	Return on Equity		Net profit After Tax / Total Equity	percentage
xii. ROI	Return on Investments		Investment Income/ Investment Assets	Percentage

First seven variables are related to income and last five variables are related to profitability. Composition of income of insurance industry and relationship between such structure and profitability is discussed on following chapter. Income from different sources, their share on overall insurance market, their growth trends are depicts by percentage method and relationship between income and profitability variables are shown by Pearson's correlation method and hypotheses has tested using inferential parametric statistics.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses about the pattern and structure, trend and market share of different sources of income earned by life insurance companies over last 5 years period (FY 2006/07 to 2011/12) of 8 life insurance companies (private sector undertakings), excluding Rastriya Beema Sansthan (a government undertaking) and the correlations among these different sources of income with profitability indicators of insurance industries in aggregate and individual.

Descriptive Statistics

The summary statistics of the income and profitability related variables has been presented in table 3. The average of two highest income sources Net Premium (NPREM) and Income from Investment, Loan and Others investment (ILIO) during 5 years period of 8 companies was NRs. 925.36 and 199.93 million respectively. Excluding the provisioned income, lowest mean income was Other Direct Income (ODI).

Net Profit Margin (NPM), Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Investment (ROI) are presented in percentage term whereas Net Profit (NP) is presented in million. Average net profit margin, ROE, ROA and ROI of industry 41.98, 14.22, 2.78 and 7 per cent respectively. These figures indicate that the earning capacity of insurance industry was good.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
NPREM	40	925.36	783.66	0.16	3,080.49
RECOMI	40	8.21	25.04	0	134.47
ILOI	40	199.93	231.13	0	929.98
LPI	40	17.22	26.40	0	126.74
ODI	40	8.19	19.91	0	123.93
POCBY	40	23.04	43.41	0	196.71
PURBY	35	26.86	38.92	0	130.75
NP	40	48.66	104.49	(66.37)	625.71

NPM	40	41.98	201.15	(2.16)	1,277.79
ROE	40	14.22	19.22	(16.12)	85.16
ROA	40	2.78	3.74	(0.82)	16.72
ROI	40	6.97	2.34	.82	19.85

Source: Calculation based on annual reports

Structure and Pattern of Income of LICs

There is no doubt that major source of income of life insurance company is net premium. However, premium is long term liability of company, but in accounting language in insurance, it is recognized as income and transferred to the life fund. During FY 2011/12, the share of net premium on total income was 73 per cent, the second highest sources is accounted as investments, loan and other income which was 19 per cent of total income and the rest of the 5 sources aggregate is less than 10 per cent. But, the structure in 2006/07 was quite different than that in 2011/12. The share of net premium in 2006/07 was 87 per cent but in 2011/12, the share decreased to 80 per cent and investments, loan and other income was 10.60 per cent in 2006/07 but increased to 14.53 per cent in 2011/12. Other sources of income also increased but their role on total income is not significant. Aggregate of remaining five sources also had increased from 2 per cent (in 2006/07) to 11 per cent (in 2011/12). As life fund increases, obviously, return on investment and interest on policy loan amount also increases. Over the period, reinsurance commission income also increased from 0.09 per cent share to almost 1 per cent share, that means the size of reinsurance also gradually increased. On the basis of total income the size of the business is increased by 29 per cent CAGR during the last 6 years. During the same period, the CAGR of Net Premium, Reinsurance Commission Income Investment, Loan and Others income has noticed 25, 76 and 39 per cent which show the growth of second highest sources of income is highly satisfactory. Appendix 3 shows structure of income from various sources of life insurance industries.

Figure 1 depicts that trend of major three income sources of Life Insurance over the last six years period. The share of net premium has decreased from 87 percent to 73 percent in contrast investment income share has increased from 10.6 to 19.29 per cent and income from policy loan also increased from 0.47 to 1.42 per cent. It is cleared that other income has been occupied the market share over premium income.

Fig.1: Trend of major three sources of life insurance income over five years period

Growth Rate of Different Sources of Income

The Compounding Average Growth rate (CAGR) of NPREM, RECOMI and ILOI was reported 26, 77 and 40 percent respectively but rest of the income have negative growth rate at least one year so the CAGR is not possible to calculate. The CAGR of aggregate income over five years period is 29 percent.

Table 4: Growth of Different Sources of Income

FY	Growth Rate							Aggregate Growth Rate
	NPREM	RECOMI	ILOI	LPI	ODI	POCBY	PURBY	
2007/08	18%	20%	21%	47%	10%	98%	N/A	19%
2008/09	40%	296%	84%	581%	20%	109%	N/A	50%
2009/10	36%	172%	52%	-43%	487%	-30%	39%	37%
2010/11	17%	127%	65%	54%	-67%	107%	234%	27%
2011/12	29%	45%	33%	40%	41%	42%	29%	31%
CAGR	26%	77%	40%	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	29%

Source: Calculation based on Annual Reports

Correlation Between Income and Profitability

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient describes the relationship between two interval and categorical variables. This tool does not explain the causes and effects of relationship among the variables but it indicates direction of movement between two variables. Correlation between different income sources is shown in Appendix 1 and correlation between each income heading and profitability indicators is shown in table 2.

The correlation matrix shows that Net Premium income has significant positive relationship with Investment, Loan and Others income (ILOI), Loan on Policyholders Income (LPI), Other income and Provision for Outstanding Claim beginning of the year (POCBY) but not significant relationship with the income from reinsurance commission (RECOMI). Except relationship between Provision for unexpired risk at the Beginning of the year (PURBY) and Other Direct Income (ODI) which is negative. Interesting thing is that in spite of increase in net premium, reinsurance commission income is not increased in same direction.

Among 21 relationships, it is noted that correlation between Return on Equity with NPREM, ILOI, LPI is found significant (positive) and rest of the variables have no significant relation each other. Assets and income sources and profit and income sources have no significant relation. This test suggested that ROE, ROA and NPM more depend on surplus which is the result of income and expenditure. As we have not included expenses in this study, we can observe the role of expenditure on these variables.

Correlation matrix (see table 5) exhibits the correlation between different types of income sources and profitability ratios.

Table 5: Correlation Matrix of Income and Profitability Variables

Profitability Variables	Income Related Variables						
	NPREM	RECOMI	ILOI	LPI	ODI	POCBY	PURBY
NPM	-0.228 (0.156)	-0.064 (0.697)	-0.169 (0.298)	-0.13 (0.424)	-0.084 (0.607)	-0.105 (0.519)	0.141 (0.419)
ROE	.522** (0.001)	0.081 (0.619)	.514** (0.001)	.313* (0.049)	0.041 (0.804)	0.131 (0.422)	0.232 (0.179)
ROA	-0.265 (0.098)	-0.104 (0.524)	-0.279 (0.082)	-0.303 (0.057)	-0.217 (0.178)	-0.226 (0.162)	0.288 (0.099)

Source: Annual Reports, FY 2007/08 – 2011/12, calculation is based on PASW 18

This paper explores that net premium is major income of all companies but interesting result we can see negative correlation between Net premium and Net Profit and Return on Asset. The relation is positive with Return on Equity which is significant also. This may happen due to the increase in expenditure to income ratio over the period. This ratio was 31 percent in 2006/07 and increased to 40% in 200/11 and 39% in 2011/12.

Out of 7 sources of income, Net profit margin and Return on Assets are negatively correlated with 6 variables but these relationship are not significant both 1 percent and 5 percent level. Return on Equity is positively correlated with all income sources but only with 3 variables (NPREM, ILOI and LPI), it is significant. This means Equity capital doesn't increase as per the net premium increase but net premium influence on changes in amount of total assets as major portion of net premium income is a part of asset. The relationship reveals that the influence of net income is less significant than expenditure to profitability.

Income Structure of Old and New Firms

Age is an important variable that influence the earnings of the firm. In Nepalese context, we have 5 year young to 25 years old firms are doing business insurance market. Out of seven income sources, four have significant difference and rest of three have no significant difference between old and new firms.

Table 6: t Statistics of Structure of Income Source of Old and New firms

Income Type	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
NPREM	-5.032	0.000
RECOMI	1.233	0.227
ILOI	6.388	0.000
LPI	2.341	0.026
ODI	1.328	0.193
POCBY	2.234	0.032
PURBY	-0.921	0.368

Source: Calculation by Authors based on the Annual Reports

The t test statistics of structure of income source of old and new firms (table 6) reveals that the highest contributing income NPREM, second contributing income ILOI, fourth and fifth contributing income POBY and LPI have significant difference (p value is less than 0.05 of all these items) but least contributing

income sources (RECOMI, PURBY and ODI) have no significant difference since p value of t statistics is more than 0.05). This result concludes that income structure is influenced by the age of the firm.

Profitability between Old and New Firms

Financial performance is measured by four ratios. Return on Equity, Return of Assets, Net Profit Margin and Return on Investment of FY 2008/09 to 2011/12 has been compared between old and new firms. Independent t test of two categories of sample has exhibited in table 6

Table 6: Summary of t Statistics of Profitability Ratios of New and Old Firms

FY	ROA		ROE		NPM		ROI	
	t test	Sig. (2-tailed)	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
2007/08	-3.604	0.011	-0.95	0.379	-1.172	0.286	5.37	0.002
2008/09	-1.801	0.122	1.116	0.307	-2.822	0.030	0.588	0.578
2009/10	-5.329	0.002	0.63	0.552	-5.046	0.002	-1.314	0.237
2010/11	-1.814	0.120	-0.013	0.990	-2.466	0.049	-1.417	0.206
2011/12	-2.058	0.085	1.722	0.136	-1.622	0.156	-1.079	0.322

Return on Assets: The result shows that ROA of old and new firms during FY 2007/08 and 2009/10 have significant difference but rest of the years, have no significant difference.

Return on Equity: According to the p value of t statistics which is more than 0.05 in each years, we have not sufficient proof to reject the null hypothesis. It means, old and new firms have same ROE over the study period.

Net Profit Margin: During FY 2008/09 to 2010/11, NPM of old and new firms have significant difference and rest of the year, there was no differences.

Return on Investments: The p value reveals that only during the first year of the business operation of new firms, the ROI was difference between old and new firms, but after 2007/08, both firms have no significant differences on ROI.

CONCLUSION

This study has explored the structure of different types of insurance income, their share, and their trends of growth in Nepalese life insurance industry. Major sources of income are Net Premium and Investment, Loan and Others income. More than 87 percent of the total income was contributed by net premium during 2006/07 which was gradually decreased to 73 percent in 2011/12. But, investment income was 10.60 percent in 2006/07 has gradually increased to 19.29 percent in 2011/12. Rest of the five income were gradually increased their share from 2 percent to 8 percent over the six years. This fact reveals that insurance companies have been capable to explore other income sources which is an ample opportunity to increase their wealth. This changing pattern indicates the vital role of investment income profitability of the firm in long run. So that firms are required to aware on portfolio management while investing the large amount of life fund in the secure and more profitable sectors. But the share of reinsurance commission still less than 1 percent however the ratio between Reinsurance income to net premium income also gradually increased from 0.11 percent (2006/07) to 1.36 percent (2011/12).

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The study further demonstrated that income structure has significant difference between the older and younger firms. The correlation coefficient shows that Net Profit Margin and Return on Assets has negative correlation but Return on Equity has positive correlation with major income sources which described that income itself does not determine the profitability of the firms as expenditure is another most dominant factors that determine the profitability.

Another interesting fact explored by the study that profitability related measures ROI, ROE and ROA of old and new firms have no significant differences except NPM.

RECOMMENDATION

On the basis of conclusion, it is suggested to carry out further research on determinants of profitability of Nepalese life insurance industries so that insurers will get ample supports to craft their future strategies. It is further recommended to life insurers to explore the new market to increase the share of premium income as its share on total income is gradually decreasing trends. Younger firms also can perform better than old firms so that younger firm need not feel substandard themselves. Furthermore, insurers require to take precaution whether their investment fund is secured and capable to provide good return.

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